

Table 1. Implementation difficulties and reasons for the lack of implementation of the principles

Difficulties	%	Reasons	%
Purpose			
• User relationship	25	• Lack of knowledge	51,7
• Tool/engine used	12,5	• Not responsible	31
• Organizational constraints	12,5	• Not a functional requirement	13,8
• Without difficulties	50	• Not allowed by the organization	3,4
Adequacy			
• Organizational constraints	23	• Lack of knowledge	71,9
• Tool/engine used	15,4	• Not a functional requirement	15,6
• Comprehension of the functionality	7,7	• Not responsible	12,5
• Without difficulties	53,8		
Necessity			
• Define strictly necessary data	66,7	• Lack of knowledge	55,6
• Without difficulties	33,3	• Organizational or personal conflict	40
		• Not responsible	4,4
Free Access			
• User relationship	40	• Lack of knowledge	72,5
• Without difficulties	60	• Not a functional requirement	15
		• Not responsible	12,5
Data Quality			
• Tool/engine used	25	• Lack of knowledge	85,7
• Organizational constraints	4,2	• Not a functional requirement	9,5
• User relationship	4,2	• Not responsible	4,8
• Comprehension of the functionality	4,2		
• Without difficulties	62,5		
Transparency			
• Volume and separation of the data	40	• Lack of knowledge	80
• Organizational constraints	13,3	• Not a functional requirement	16,7
• Without difficulties	46,7	• Not responsible	3,3
Security			
• Tool/algorithm used	42,1	• Already implemented in the system	100
• Affected system performance	10,5		
• Without difficulties	47,4		
Prevention			
• Tool/engine used	11,1	• Lack of knowledge	69,4
• Comprehension of the functionality	11,1	• Not a functional requirement	19,4
• Operation mapping	11,1	• Not responsible	11,1
• Without difficulties	66,7		
Non-discrimination			
• User relationship	16,7	• Lack of knowledge	87,2
• Without difficulties	83,3	• Not a functional requirement	7,7
		• Not responsible	5,1
Accountability			
• Operation mapping	28,6	• Lack of knowledge	81,6
• Tool/engine used	14,3	• Not a functional requirement	15,8
• Without difficulties	57,1	• Not responsible	2,6